

ISic000640

I.Sicily inscription 000640

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

None

Last Change

2021-07-02 - Francesca Prado tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Found by Dr Pr. Cacia 'in un suo podere'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, private collection (P. Cacia)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Πουβλειλί α ἰ Ἀγάθιν ἰ

3. χρηστά · χαῖρε ·

4. ἔζησεν ἔτη · λγ ·

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Publilia Agathin! She lived for 33 years.

Translation (it)

Addio, degna Publilia Agathin! Ella visse 33 anni.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644882

EDR 141111

EDCS 64800567

PHI 332878

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic000640>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4385084](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385084)

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0763

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0746

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 85 no.3b

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2021-07-14): ISic000640. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101183>